

Machu Picchu

also known as “Machu Pikchu”

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Entry tags: Sacred mountain, Peak Sanctuaries, Inkas, Sacred Territory, Quechuan, Religious Group, Ritual centre, Language, Religious Place

Machu Pikchu was a prominent Inka royal estate in a unique environmental context between the highlands of the Cuzco region and the Amazon. It had a range of spaces - religious, domestic, and public.

Date Range: 1420 CE - 1532 CE

Region: Machu Pikchu Area

Region tags: Peru, Andes

This area displayed here includes Machu Pikchu (Machu Picchu) as well as associated regional sites, such as Wayna Pikchu (Huayna Picchu), the Temple of the Moon, Inkaraqay, Intipunku, and Phutuq K'usi.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Salazar, Lucy. “Machu Picchu: Mysterious Royal Estate in the Cloud Forest.” In *Machu Picchu: Unveiling the Mystery of the Incas*, edited by Richard Burger and Lucy Salazar, 21-47. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2004.
- Source 2: Burger, Richard, Lucy Salazar, Jason Nesbitt, Eden Washburn, and Lars Fehren-Schmitz. “New AMS Dates for Machu Picchu: Results and Implications.” *Antiquity* 95, no. 383 (2021): 1265-79. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.15184/aqy.2021.99>.
- Source 3: Verano, John. “Human Skeletal Remains from Machu Picchu: A Reexamination of the Yale Peabody Museum’s Collection.” In *The 1912 Yale Peruvian Scientific Expedition Collections from Machu Picchu: Human and Animal Remains*, edited by Richard Burger and Lucy Salazar, 65-117. New Haven: Yale Peabody Museum, 2003.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190219352.013.41>.

– Source 1 Description: Quave, Kylie. “Royal Estates and Imperial Centers in the Cuzco Region.” In *The Oxford Handbook of the Incas*, edited by Sonia Alconini and R. Alan Covey, 101–18. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018.

– Source 2 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190219352.013.40>

– Source 2 Description: Burger, Richard, and Lucy Salazar. “Reinventing the Incas in Contemporary Cuzco: The Cases of Inti Raymi and Machu Picchu.” In *The Oxford Handbook of the Incas*, edited by Sonia Alconini and R. Alan Covey, 807–28. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018.

– Source 3 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1179/naw.2010.30.1.1>.

– Source 3 Description: Lee, Vincent. “Choquequirao to Machu Picchu at the Speed of Light: Visual Signaling among the Incas.” *Ñawpa Pacha* 30, no. 1 (2010): 1–24.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1912

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: The 1912 Yale Peruvian Scientific Expedition

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Water feature

– Other [specify]: Architectural complementing of natural landscapes

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

- ↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
– No

- ↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: Many features

- ↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ A group of features:
– Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Other [specify]: Communal and Individual

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

- Field doesn't know

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Presumably Inti, the supreme sun god of the Inka, was a factor.

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This was an Inka royal estate, thus it would have been dedicated to an Inka emperor, who would have qualified as a semi-divine human being.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

– Corvee labourers

– Indentured servants

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Inka state.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Preservation has not maintained total heights of buildings.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Preservation has not maintained total dimensions of buildings.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– Field doesn't know
Notes: Preservation has not maintained total heights of monuments.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some are, some are not.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Some are, some are not.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Technically yes, highly geometric construction blocks.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Mummies of past emperors were paraded around and traveled, so within this logic the place could have been visited by deceased emperors. However, Machu Picchu was not a place for literally worshipping the dead.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Perishable artifacts

↳ Other

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Technically Inti was present at all Inka sites, although his distinct representational form beyond a temple structure is not demonstrated.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably, in the form of paraded mummified Inka emperors who visited.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably, but this is not proven ethnohistorically or archaeologically.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: When Inka emperors would visit, they are human-divine beings. This was a royal Inka emperor estate.

Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: When an Inka emperor was physically present.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably as this is a royal Inka estate and Inka emperor's were divine descendants of Inti, the sun god.

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Presumably the population of Machu Pikchu

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Presumably during calendrical events

Notes: Guaman Poma de Ayala ([1615] 1936) outlines many of these.

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

- Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

- No

Are material offerings present:

- Yes

- ↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Metal statuary and precious ceramics are often found here.

- ↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Domestic cooking vessels have been documented.

- ↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Often in cave deposits.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Perishable artifacts

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The sponsorship emperor of Machu Pikchu and kin

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Yes, particularly by yanakuna - elite imperial servants

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– Yes

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Local yanakuna (servant population) may have sponsored personalized commemorations.

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Yes

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably, but this is not definitively known.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Machu Picchu Area

Bibliography

General References

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